

**A WEB APPLICATION FOR COMMUNICATION BETWEEN
MEDICAL STAFF AND PATIENTS IN MEDICAL PRACTICE.**

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Abstract: The quality of medical care depends on effective communication between medical staff and patients. Good communication not only speeds up the healing process, but also improves the patient's mental state. Today, thanks to the development of technology, there are several systems in the medical field that provide communication between doctors and patients. This article talks about one such system, the “Medical consultant” application.

Keywords: Information systems, medical consultant, web application, use case diagram, interface.

Enter

Currently, medical literacy in our society is not at a high level. If someone has a fever, a headache, or feels the symptoms of some illness, he does not know what to do in this situation, which doctor to consult. In this situation, it is necessary to organize quick consultations with doctors so that they do not arbitrarily and hastily carry out wrong treatment.

Today, almost all regions of our republic are provided with fast internet services. But it is not so easy to use the services of qualified medical personnel and doctors who provide fast and quality service or conduct medical consultation. It is not so difficult for patients to talk to doctors and receive medical consultation. Then the doctor listens to the problems, analyzes them and gives his medical advice and recommendations.

The site is intended for doctors and patients of a private clinic, and at first it serves to enable the patient to easily search for doctors of any specialty. After receiving the

necessary treatments from the doctor, the patient who comes to the doctor's appointment, serves to get advice from the doctor about the processes taking place in him.

Analysis of automated systems.

Below is an analysis of automated systems used in the medical field and their importance in medical practice:

- Electronic Medical Records (EMR) is a system that provides quick access and storage of all medical information about patients. Through the EMR, doctors can view a patient's medical history, treatment regimens, allergies, and other important information. Through this system, effective communication between doctors and patients is established, they get complete information about the patient's treatment and help in making important medical decisions.

- Telemedicine is a technology that enables remote communication between doctors and patients. Through this system, doctors can communicate with patients through video calls, chats and other online platforms. Telemedicine is especially important for patients living in remote areas, as they are able to receive professional medical care without leaving their homes.

- Mobile applications. Today, many mobile applications are effectively used in the medical field. Through these applications, patients can track their medical information, communicate with their doctor, and receive medical advice. For example, applications such as MyChart, Medscape, Epocrates facilitate communication between doctors and patients and provide efficient management.

Stages of application development.

Steps to develop an application that provides communication between doctors and patients:

- Requirement's analysis. The first step is to organize communication between doctors and patients and analyze their requirements and needs. This is very important in defining the functional requirements and interface of the application.

- Design. Next, after studying the requirements, the design of the application interface is developed. This includes creating an ergonomic design that is user-friendly and easy to use.
- Backend part. A backend part will be developed to store and manage all the data in the application that provides communication between doctors and patients.
- Frontend part. F should create a user-friendly interface, provide opportunities for users to communicate with doctors and use the program easily.
- Message protocols. It is known what communication protocols and methods should be used and how they should be facilitated to communicate between doctors and patients. Practical experience testing and optimization for these protocols is essential.
- Testing. Testing the application the process of verifying that the application works correctly and fully meets the requirements.
- Data protection. Doctors and patients are vulnerable individuals, and it is important to protect their personal information. Adequate security parameters and protocols must be applied to protect this data.
- Submit the created application. Providing the application to users and their usage process. It includes proper marketing strategies, presentation to the users, a lot related to the program.

The use case diagram of the application represents the relationship between the user, patient, admin and other visitors. As seen in this use case diagram, an admin can control statistics and users. Ordinary users can use the system to register, log in, search, and filter (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Use case diagram.

Using the application

For each part of the application that enables communication between doctors and patients, and in general, it is important to provide a user-friendly and reliable experience.

It requires the user to enter their username and password to log in. The system automatically detects the entered parameters and determines whether he is a doctor or a doctor.

Visitors to the site will initially receive general information about doctors. Based on this information, patients can find the doctors they need. It is also possible to search

for doctors by regions and specialties. With this convenience, you can quickly find the right doctor-specialist in a convenient way (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. The program's search window.

Later, after choosing a doctor, the patient will have complete information about him and can go to the chat window to communicate (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Start a chat.

After the patient has information about the doctor, he can directly communicate with the doctor (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Chat window.

In general, the creation of such an application encourages patients to be more attentive to their health, and eases the work process of doctors and improves the quality of medical services. This helps to strengthen the public's trust in the health care system.

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